

Studies on β -4-Chlorobenzoylacrylic Acid. Formation of Chalkones by Meerwein's Arylation Method and of Adducts with various Amines

H. S. Mehra

Arylation of β -4-chlorobenzoylacrylic acid with various diazonium chlorides under the conditions of Meerwein's diazo reaction affords 4'-chloro-chalkones. The yields of chalkones show that the reactivity of chloro-substituted acid is of the same order as that of the parent acid. Further adducts of this acid with benzylamine and some aromatic amines have been prepared.

In previous communications, we have described arylations by diazonium salts under the conditions of Meerwein's diazo reaction of certain β -aroyl acrylic acids e.g. β -benzoyl²-, β -4-methoxy-benzoyl³-, β -3-4 dimethoxybenzoyl-, β -2-methoxy-5-methylbenzoyl⁴-acrylic acids. The products are chalkones formed according to the equation :

The present communication records the results of condensing various diazonium chlorides with β -4-chloro benzoyl acrylic acid under the conditions of Meerwein's diazo reaction with a view to studying the influence of the halogen substituent para to the activating carbonyl group.

Benzene, *p*- and *o*-chloro, *p*-bromo, *p*-methoxy-, and *p*-methylbenzene diazonium chlorides have been allowed to react with β -4-chloro-benzoyl acrylic acid in presence of acetone, cupric chloride and sodium acetate. Decarboxylation occurs in every case during coupling. The chalkones formed are recovered by extraction with sodium bisulphite and subsequent basification with alkali as described earlier^{2,3}. The yields of chalkones are listed in table I. The yields from *p*-chloro and *p*-bromo diazonium chlorides are 27.5% and 20% respectively, while with other diazonium chlorides these range from 7% to 8.25%, when 0.25*M* quantities of the reactants are used. From the preparatory point of view, however, it is advisable to use an excess of diazotised amine. Prolonged extraction of the reaction mixture with sodium bisulphite is also found necessary to effect complete recovery of the resultant chalkones. Thus the yields of chalkones from *p*-chloro and *p*-bromo benzene

1. H. Meerwein, E. Buchner and K. Emster, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1939, **152**, 237.
2. H. S. Mehra and K. B. L. Mathur, *This Journal*, 1955, **32**, 465.
3. H. S. Mehra and K. B. L. Mathur, *This Journal*, 1956, **33**, 618.
4. V. P. Chachra, D. R. Sharma, H. S. Mehra and K. B. L. Mathur, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, **9**, 388.

diazonium chlorides could be improved to 30% and 22% respectively and from *p*-chloro and unsubstituted benzene diazonium chlorides to 10% each when 0.025*M* of β -4-chloro-benzoyl acrylic acid was allowed to condense with 0.33*M* of diazotised amine.

TABLE I

Interaction of various diazonium chlorides with β -4-chloro benzoyl acrylic acid.

Amine diazotised	Alkali insol. matter	Crude chalkone yield%	X	Cryst. form	Found	M.P°	Lit.
1. Aniline	4.8 g	0.48 g 8.27% (10%)*	H	EtOH yellowish cryst.	98°		15 96
2. <i>p</i> -chloro-aniline	4.6 g	1.90 g 27.5% (30%)*	Cl	EtOH yellowish needles	157-8°		16 156-7
3. <i>o</i> -chloro-aniline	5.2 g	0.48 g (7.0%)	Cl	MeOH yellowish brown cryst.	80-2°		17a&b 85-6
4. <i>p</i> -bromo-aniline	4.4 g	1.55 g (20%) (22%)*	Br	EtOH slightly yellow	173° found C, 56.01%, H, 3.4%		Calculated C, 55.98 H, 3.11% 18
5. <i>p</i> -methoxy aniline (Anisidine)	5.4 g	0.5 g 7.3% (10%)*		-OCH ₃ MeOH yellow cryst.	122-3° mixed m.p. with authentic sample		124-5 124
6. <i>p</i> -methyl aniline (toluidine)	4.5 g	0.44 g 7.0%		CH ₃ EtOH yellow cryst.	162-3°		19 165

(*improved yields.)

It is observed that the reactive benzene diazonium chloride, which almost failed to react with the parent acid², affords the chloro chalkone in 10% yield. The following table gives the comparative yields of chalkones with β -benzoyl acrylic acid² and β -4-chloro benzoyl acrylic acid respectively.

Amine diazotised (0.025 <i>M</i>)	β -benzoyl acrylic acid	β -4-chloro-benzoyl acrylic acid	
1. Benzene diazonium chloride	traces	8.27%	(10.0%)*
2. <i>p</i> -chloro benzene diazonium chloride	27.3%	27.5%	(30.0%)*
3. <i>o</i> -chloro benzene diazonium chloride	4.6%	7.0%	(10.0%)*
4. <i>p</i> -bromo benzene diazonium chloride	16.6%	20.0%	(22.0%)*

(*improved yields)

It is generally believed^{5,6,7,8} that Meerwein's diazo reaction, which is essentially a free radical reaction, proceeds via the intermediate formation of a transition complex

5. C. S. Rondstvedt (Jr.), *Organic Reactions*, Vol. XI, (John Wiley & Sons Inc. New York) 1960, 194-8.

6. G. N. Schranzer, *Chem. Ber.*, 1961, **94**, 1891-8.

7. C. F. Koelsch and V. Boekelheide, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 412.

8. O. Vogl and C. S. Rondstvedt (Jr.), *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 3800.

between the benzoyl acrylic acid, copper salt and diazonium compound. This naturally would call for the electron-donating (basic) character of the carbonyl group. The greater the basic character, the more stable will be the transition complex leading to higher yields of chalkones. From the table it is however seen that except in the reaction with benzene diazonium chloride, the yields of chalkones are more or less of the same order both from the unsubstituted and substituted acids. This shows that β -4-chloro-benzoyl acrylic acid has almost the same degree of reactivity as is found in the parent β -benzoyl acrylic acid. This is consistent with the fact that the chlorine has only a feeble (-I) effect and a (+E) effect and will have no substantial effect on the reactivity. It may be mentioned that 4-bromo-4'-chloro chalkone has been synthesised for the first time in the present study.

β -4-chloro-benzoyl acrylic acid was further condensed with some amines. The adducts were obtained with the same ease as some of the similar compounds obtainable with the parent acid. The condensations have been carried out with aniline, *p*-chloro-aniline, *p*-bromo-aniline and benzylamine. The adduct from *p*-chloro-aniline has feeble bacteriostatic action against gram-positive bacteria.

EXPERIMENTAL

β -4-chloro benzoyl acrylic acid was prepared by condensation of chloro benzene with maleic anhydride in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride⁴.

Coupling reactions with β -4-chloro-benzoyl acrylic acid:—The diazotised base (0.025*M*) was added to β -4-chloro-benzoyl acrylic acid (5.25 g, 0.025*M*) in acetone (35-40 ml) containing sodium acetate (8 g) and cupric chloride (1 g in 5 ml of water). There was brisk effervescence and the mixture was stirred for 2 hr. It was kept overnight, when the green aqueous layer separated from the dark brown mass. The reaction mixture was steam distilled to remove chloro-acetone and Sandemyer's type of products. The residue was poured in a beaker while still hot and cooled. Concentrated hydrochloric acid (1-2 ml) was added to it. The solid was separated by filtration and triturated with aqueous sodium bicarbonate (20 ml). Acidification of the bicarbonate extract afforded mostly unchanged acrylic acid. The residue left after the bicarbonate extraction was triturated with 2% caustic soda (20 ml). The alkaline mixture was filtered and washed. The alkali insoluble residue was digested with saturated sodium bisulphite (20 ml) for 3 hr and diluted with equal volume of water. It was allowed to stand for 1 hr filtered and basified with strong (60%) caustic soda. The crude chalkone was filtered, washed and dried. It was crystallised with appropriate solvent.

The yields of chalkones were improved by condensing (0.033*M*) of diazotised base with β -4-chloro benzoyl acrylic acid (5.26 g, 0.025*M*) under similar conditions. The alkali insoluble residue was digested with saturated sodium bisulphite (30 ml) for 5 hr. and basified as before with strong alkali. The yields with *p*-chloro and *p*-bromo benzene diazonium

9. M. M Fraser and R. A. Raphael, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 2245.
10. J. Bougault, P. Chabrier, *Compt. rend.*, 1950, **230**, 212; 1953, **237**, 1420.
11. W. L. Meyer and W. R. Vaughan, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, **22**, 1562.
12. N. H. Cromwell, P. L. Creger, and K. E. Cook, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 4412.
13. W. C. Johnson, and W. E. Heinz, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 2916.
14. D. Papa, E. Schwenk, F. Villani and E. Klingsberg, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3356.

chlorides were improved upon from 27.5% and 20% to 30% and 22% respectively and with benzene diazonium chloride and *o*-chloro benzene diazonium chloride from 8.27% and 7.3% to 10.0% each by the revised procedure.

The identity of chalkones from aniline and *p*-anisidine were further confirmed by preparing authentic^{15,18} specimens and by mixed m.p.s.

Preparation of adducts of β -4-chloro-benzoyl acrylic acid with amine :

The method adopted for the preparation was more or less the same as used in preparing the adducts from β -benzoyl acrylic acid¹⁰. To a solution of β -4-chloro benzoyl acrylic acid (1 g, .005M) in alcohol (12 ml) was added the required amount of amine (.005M). After shaking for sometime, the reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 48 hr. when the solid separated. In case of aniline, the solid separated after half an hour. In benzylamine, the addition was effected in acetone. The solid was filtered and crystallised from appropriate solvents. The adducts were α -aryl or benzyl amino - β -(*p*-chloro benzoyl) propionic acid^{9,12} formed thus:

TABLE II

Adducts of various amines with β -4-chlorobenzoyl acrylic acid

Amine (.005M)	Wt. of crude adduct	Colour & state	m.p.	Found	Calc.
Aniline	0.45 g	yellowish wooly flakes from alcohol	152-3	C=63.31% H=4.9%	C=63.2% H=4.6%
<i>p</i> -chloroaniline	0.5 g	yellow needles from alcohol	210	C=56.59% H=4.0%	C=56.8% H=3.8%
<i>p</i> -bromo-aniline	0.55 g	yellow crystals from alcohol	217	C=51.3% H=3.7%	C=50.2% H=3.2%
Benzylamine	1.10 g	white crystals from methanol	176	C=63.54% H=5.5%	C=64.2% H=5.0%

The author desires to express his thanks to Prof. T. R. Seshadri, F.R.S., and Prof. K.B.L. Mathur, University of Delhi, for their kind interest, to Dr. B. M. Bhatia for facilities and to the University Grants Commission for financial assistance.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
HINDU COLLEGE,
DELHI-7.

Received, June 5, 1967.

15. C. F. H. Allen and G. P. Frame, *Can. J. Res.*, 1932, **6**, 605.
16. F. Straus and A. Ackermann, *Ber.*, 1909, **42**, 1804.
17. (a) G. E. Mccasland, E. Blanz (Jr.) and A. Furst, *J. Org. Chem.* 1959, **24**, 999.
(b) C. K. Bradsher, F. C. Brown and W. B. Blue, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 3570.
18. F. G. Baddar and S. Sherif, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 2310.
19. R. B. Kanthi and K. S. Nargund, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1959, 8067 (*J. Karnatak Univ.* 1957, **2**, 8-13).